

PETER'S TRIPLE DENIAL OF CHRIST “And the Lord Turned, and Looked upon Peter”

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Abstract: This article makes an attempt to study the Apostle Peter's relationship with the Lord, particular attention being paid to Lk 22:61a. The two verbs “turned” and “looked” in juxtaposition are arresting. What kind of a “look” did the Lord give? Was it accusatory? scornful? Surprised? Or with a touch of amusement, of humour? The article suggests that it is perhaps the last, although hitherto generally seen as a look of sorrow in the light of Isaiah 53 where Christ is described as a “man of sorrows, and acquainted with grief.” However, Ezra Pound's [1885-1972] poem ‘Ballad of the Goodley Fere’ based on the four Gospels depicts a Lord and Master who has other features as well. Written in 1909 when Ezra Pound was 24, the poem captures these aspects of Christ with keen insight.

Keywords: Peter's Denial, Ezra Pound, Ballad of the Goodley Fere, Luke 22:61.

The main point of this paper is a close examination of Peter's denial of Christ three times: in Matthew 26:33-35, 69-75; Mark 14:29-31, 66-72; Luke 22:31-34, 54-62; and in John 18:25-27. Of the four gospel writers, John's account is terse, merely stating twice that Peter stood with his accusers “and warmed himself” (Jn 18:18, 25-27) and that “Peter then denied again: and immediately the cock crew,” no mention being made of his repentance.¹

¹ We will return to the undertones of this tense relationship between the two apostles later in this essay.

Both Matthew and Mark tell us that Peter remembered the Lord's prediction that he would deny him thrice, Matthew and Luke stating that he "wept bitterly," and Mark states that he "wept." Only Luke felt it imperative that he give us not only these details but also that, in addition, when "the Lord turned, and looked upon Peter [he] remembered the word of the Lord... and went out, and wept bitterly."²

Luke's account of Peter's triple denial is the most comprehensive. This is not surprising since, being a medical practitioner, a "physician" (Col 4:14), highly qualified, he must have examined minutely the accounts given to him by the "eyewitnesses" on whom he relied (Lk 1:1-2). His meticulous attention to the writing of history again appears at the beginning of the opening chapter of *The Acts of the Apostles* in which Peter prominently features as a leader after Christ's ascension "into heaven" (vv. 13, 15).

Consequently, Luke's qualifications as author of the longest synoptic gospel should prompt us to think of Peter as a character whose conduct in various contexts is open to inspection and analysis. Charismatic and assertive, these features appear prominently in their depiction of Peter in the narratives by all four Gospel writers.

The first instance appears early in his contact with the Lord when, after toiling "all the night," the fishermen failed to catch a single fish, but on being told by him to repeat the venture, they caught "a great multitude of fishes." Recognizing his divine identity, and impetuous, "when Simon Peter saw it, he fell down at Jesus' knees, saying, Depart from me; for I am a sinful man, O Lord" (Lk 5:4-8).

The second instance occurs when, seeing the Lord "walking on the sea," the disciples "were troubled, saying, It is a spirit; and they cried out for fear." But not Peter: "Lord, if it be thou, bid me come unto thee on the water. And he said, Come." We all know what happened thereafter: "But when

² "Then the Lord turned back, and looked upon Peter ...And Peter went out, & wept bitterly": *The Geneva Bible* (1560). "Turning round" in J. N. Darby's translation (1867) and the *Revised Version* (1881). All quotations in this paper are from the *Authorised Version* (1611).

he saw the wind boisterous, he was afraid; and beginning to sink, he cried, saying, Lord, save me” (Mt 14:24-30).

The third instance happens when Peter is aghast at the very thought of his Master washing his feet: “Lord, dost thou wash my feet? Thou shalt never wash my feet.” Abashed by the Lord’s gentle rebuke – “If I wash thee not, thou hast no part with me” – Peter immediately accepts the corrective (Jn 13:6-8).

The fourth instance happens when Peter draws his sword and cuts off the ear of Malchus (John being the only writer who names both men) and is reprimanded by the Lord: “Put up thy sword into the sheath: the cup which my Father hath given me, shall I not drink it?” (Jn 18:10-11).³

Before we come to Peter’s triple denial of Christ, a controversy arises among the disciples as to “which of them should be accounted the greatest,” Peter’s claim, expectedly, being the most strident, for the Lord affectionately reproves only him, none of the others:, and warns him of the portentous development ahead, as his double utterance of Peter’s first name indicates, “Simon, Simon, behold, Satan hath desired to have you, that he may sift you as wheat: But I have prayed for thee, that thy faith fail not” (Lk 22:31-32). Merrill C. Tenney points out that “wheat was sifted to remove the dirt and chaff, and to eliminate the broken and withered grains. The temptations of the devil often serve the purpose of revealing strength as well as weakness in believers.”⁴

Some of us might have witnessed ‘sifting’ done in the rural parts of India before technology displaced this manual exercise. It was carried out with a woven cane basket in which the operator tossed the wheat while standing aslant of the wind which blew away the chaff and other impurities. Further clarification of this important episode may be seen in J. N. Darby’s commentary in which an analysis is offered

³ These four familiar instances of Peter’s spontaneity are listed in chronological order for the light they shed on Peter’s relationship with the Lord.

⁴ Merrill C. Tenney, “The Gospel According to Luke,” in *The Wycliffe Bible Commentary*, ed. Charles F. Pfeiffer and Everett F. Harrison (Chicago: Moody Press, 1968), 1064.

of Satan's interest in testing Peter's spiritual stamina. The Lord's death now Imminent, he would shortly be leaving the disciples to fend for themselves,

What an opportunity for the enemy to sift them since they could no longer follow Him as men living on the earth! All that belonged to a living Messiah was completely overthrown, and death was there. Who could pass through it? Satan would profit by this, and desired to have them that he might sift them. Jesus does not seek to spare His disciples this sifting.⁵

Still confident and unfazed, Peter dismisses the warning, declaring, "Lord, I am ready to go with thee, both into prison, and to death," and, therefore, needs to be somewhat deflated! It is difficult not to detect an element of amusement as well as affection for his disciple's sturdy confidence: "I tell thee, Peter, The cock shall not crow this day, before that thou shalt thrice deny that thou knowest me" (Lk 22:33, 34). Shortly following this dialogue is Peter's third denial, "Man, I know not what thou sayest," and "immediately while he yet spake, the cock crew" – and we come to the central point of this paper – "And the Lord turned, and looked upon Peter." We shall attempt a possible, even perhaps a probable, expansion of "turned" and "looked" in this detail (Lk 22:60-61).

However, before doing so, an interjection seems necessary. Of course, from one point of view, Peter's denial is shocking; but was the Lord shocked? Certainly not, for he had accurately warned Peter of his forthcoming denial. This scene offers us a dual perspective: ours and the Lord's, and there is a vast difference between the two. Further, despite Peter's triple denial, he did not decamp as a coward would have, but resolutely stayed on in the danger zone. The scene is complex, embodying the opposites of courage and cowardice that the Lord recognized, taking into account Peter's inner struggle and judging him, as hinted above, not harshly but kindly. Christ's recognition of these two facets that make him so fascinating a figure, and calls for a

⁵ J. N. Darby, *Synopsis of the Books of the Bible. Vol. III, Matthew — John*, new edition — revised (London: G. Morrish, n.d.), 369.

reappraisal of our approach which will be developed in the following section.

We have here two verbs, “turned” and “looked,” each complementary to the other. Clearly, the author wants the reader to pause and ponder. Both verbs are in tandem, “turned” implying a deliberate act, and “looked” leaving it to the reader to speculate on the kind of look the Lord gave. Was it accusatory, angry, scornful? Did it imply ‘You are a coward and a boaster’? None of these, I suggest. Rather, it seems to me that his look had a touch of sympathy because of the accuracy of his prediction, accompanied by a nod of encouragement, a recognition of human frailty. It was precisely this gracious accommodation, without reproach, of Peter’s over confidence that was the reason for his having “wept *bitterly*” [italics added], the adverb being of vital importance in context, stressing his anguish for having betrayed his compassionate Lord and Master.

As we recall, a short while earlier the Lord had said to Peter, “What, could ye not watch with me one hour?” the tone not being condemnatory but kindly, followed by the exculpatory analysis: “The spirit indeed is willing, but the flesh is weak,” is his generous exhortation for the embarrassed disciples, especially Peter (Mt 26:40). This brief episode, a prelude to the test in which Peter was a failure, shows how ready the Lord was to justify his disciples despite their weakness, a quality later recognized by the apostle Paul writing to Titus, “that being justified by his grace, we should be made heirs according to the hope of eternal life” (Tit 3:7).

Consequently, I am emboldened to suggest that the Lord could well have given Peter a friendly smile, and it may not be too farfetched to go back 2000 years and speculate that even in that distant context this could have been plausible, for Paul, addressing the men of Athens on Mars Hill a few years later had warned them against idolatry with these words, “We ought not to think that the Godhead is like unto gold, or silver, or stone, graven by art and man’s device.

And the times of this ignorance God winked⁶ [AV, 1611] at; but now commandeth all men everywhere to repent” (Acts 17:29-30). Both attitudes are comparable, that of the Lord to Peter and that of Paul to the Athenians, reflecting not severity but leniency. The verb “winked” that the translators of the *Authorised Version* used implies that in 17th-century England it was in current usage as meaning ‘overlooked.’ Whereas today it may seem too frivolous for comfort, it is likely that in Palestine of the first century A.D., it was acceptable as well.

The deep and close relationship between the Lord and Peter is further endorsed in the last chapter of John’s gospel describing his appearance standing “on the shore” after his resurrection, while the disciples pursued their profession as fishermen. As already noted in this paper, a similar situation had arisen earlier but on this occasion John recognized the Master first, telling Peter, “It is the Lord.” Impulsive as before, “he girt his fisher’s coat unto him (for he was naked), and did cast himself into the sea” (Jn 21:7).

This is followed by the Lord’s triple interrogation of Peter – “Simon, son of Jonas, lovest thou me more than these?” (vv.15-17) – an inverse repetition of Peter’s triple denial of Christ so as to discipline him through this painful reminder into later becoming one of the greatest apostles of the Christian doctrine of salvation being offered without discrimination to one and all (Acts 10:9-43) and “the rock” upon which the Church would be built (Mt 16:18 and Jn 1:42).

Here, still irrepressible, outspoken, and competitive with John, “the disciple whom Jesus loved” (Jn 13:23), for

⁶ “And the time of this ignorance God regarded not: but now he admonisheth all men everywhere to repent” (*Geneva Bible*). “Overlooked” both in J. N. Darby and the *Revised Version* and so noted in *The Wycliffe Bible Commentary*, 1157. In “winked at,” “regarded not,” and “overlooked,” we have a cluster of synonymous verbs not punitive – it seems to me – but complaisant, the stress being on salvation, a cheerful prospect. And contemplating the murder of Duncan, Macbeth’s [in Shakespeare’s play first published in the *Folio* of 1623] aside, “Stars, hide your fires! / Lest not light see my black and deep desires; / The eye wink at the hand” (I,iv, 49-51), gives to “wink” the sense of ‘to be blind to.’ Ed. Kenneth Muir (London: Arden, Methuen, 1969).

having recognized the Lord before he did, Peter ironically asks, "Lord, and what shall this man do?" the Lord's reply is tolerant, though stern: "If I will that he tarry till I come, what is that to thee? follow thou me" (Jn 21:22). We have already noted that John alone among the Gospel writers makes no mention of Peter's repentance for his denial of Christ. Clearly, there was an element of rivalry between them for the Lord's approval, thus showing them to be susceptible to human feelings while at the same time having his authority for the formulation of sound doctrine in their epistles, as well as for John in his Gospel, the opening verses announcing the Incarnation and echoing the majestic beginning of the book of Genesis. (For a later harmonious relationship between the two apostles, see Acts 3:1-11).

Nevertheless, it seems to me that the earlier tension between these two great apostles calls for our close scrutiny and analysis in accord with Peter's own declaration that the words of scripture were given to "holy men of God . . . as they were moved by the Holy Ghost" (2 Peter 1:21). The apostle John describes himself thrice, the first time as the disciple "whom Jesus loved" (Jn 13:23); the second time while "standing by" the cross as "the disciple . . . whom he loved" (Jn 19:26); and the third time, "Then Peter, turning about, seeth the disciple whom Jesus loved following; which also leaned on his breast at supper" (Jn 21:20). It is important for us to note that *only* John stresses his unique relationship with the Lord as the disciple "whom Jesus loved."

While a schoolboy I remember my puzzlement at this triple reiteration and asked my father – an internationally recognized historian with a Cambridge University degree and later Professor of History at Rangoon University – whether John was the Lord's favourite disciple, and his reply was to the effect that the Lord had no favourites, but that John himself had a strong sense of the Lord's love for him and, accordingly, responded in this manner.

Further, he advised me to study the references to Judas Iscariot who betrayed Jesus, especially Mk 14:18 ("Verily I

say unto you, one of you which eateth with me shall betray me”) but the Lord did not demote him from his rank of apostleship, an astonishing attitude of grace and tolerance.

Yet it is important for us to remain aware that despite the Lord’s affection for and leniency towards Peter, and even Judas Iscariot, there was no question of his permitting the divine plan of salvation for all through his death and resurrection being thwarted by Satan’s wiles in using Peter as an instrument of disruption. This is seen in Christ’s unsparing and amazing reprimand of Peter (Mt 16:21-23 and Mk 8:31-33) who at this point of time had no inkling of the cataclysmic events to follow and so, in ignorance, began to “rebuke” his Lord and Master for predicting his coming death and resurrection at the hands of “the elders and chief priests and scribes,” addressing him as “Satan” – a reprimand that must have shocked Peter: “Get thee behind me, Satan: thou art an offence unto me: for thou savourest not the things that be of God, but those that be of men,” especially so because in the same chapter (Mt 16:16-17) he had been blest by Christ for recognizing him as “the Son of the living God.”

Apart from a few variations among the four gospel writers, a phenomenological feature that police investigators in road accident situations point out, is proof of the authenticity of each witness’s Impression – in fact, if there is uniformity, it has been doctored!

Returning to our consideration of Peter’s repentance when he “wept bitterly,” some readers might agree that despite the gravity of Peter’s situation as Satan’s victim, the Lord’s subtle sense of humour, hinted at earlier in this paper, remains unimpaired and despite the anger of the authorities being roused against him for having driven out the money making mercenaries from the temple with the words, “Is it not written My house shall be called of all nations the house of prayer? but ye have made it a den of thieves” (Mk 11:15-18; see also Jn 2:13-17), when challenged by the scribes and chief priests, “By what authority doest thou these things?” his reply is a counter question: “I will also ask of

you one question, and answer me . . . The baptism of John [the Baptist], was it from heaven, or of men? answer me.” Disconcerted, “they reasoned with themselves, saying, If we say from Heaven; he will say, Why then did ye not believe him? But if we shall say, of men; they feared the people; for all men counted John, that he was a prophet indeed. And they answered and said unto Jesus “We cannot tell,” “Jesus answering saith unto them [perhaps with a chuckle] Neither do I tell you by what authority I do these things” – a mischievous tit for tat that effectively silences them.

This aspect of Jesus’ personality, generally unknown, has been noted by William F. Hansen,⁷ who points out that in the Greek and Latin translations of the Bible “puns are unrecognizable . . . one thinks of Jesus’ Aramaic puns which get lost in the Greek of the New Testament.”⁸

The general feeling among both Christians and others is that Christ was humourless. This view is mainly based on the old Testament prophesy in Isaiah 53, “He is despised and rejected of men; a man of sorrows, and acquainted with grief” (v. 3), but the American poet Ezra Pound (1885-1972), basing his poem on the four Gospels, gives us a Christ who was humorous, witty, ironic, and often sarcastic. In his poignant and deeply moving poem ‘Ballad of the Goodly Fere: Simon Zelotes speaketh it sometime after the Crucifixion,’⁹ the poet captures wonderfully well this aspect of the Lord. Simon Zelotes was one of the twelve apostles (Lk 6:15) from Cyrene, a city in Libya adjacent to Egypt, and having been “compelled to bear his cross” on the way to Golgotha (see Mt 27: 32-33; Mk 15:21; Lk 23:26), he was possibly a black African of mixed blood – Greek, Egyptian.

⁷ Hansen, William F. *Saxo Grammaticus and the Life of Hamlet: A Translation, History and Commentary* (Lincoln and London: Univ. of Nebraska Pr., 1983), 40.

⁸ Robert H. Stein, *The Method and Message of Jesus’ Teachings* (Philadelphia: Westminster Pr., 1978), 76-78.

⁹ Ezra Pound, “Ballad of the Goodly Fere: Simon Zelotes speaketh it sometime after the Crucifixion,” in *The Conscious Voice: An Anthology of American Poetry from the Seventeenth Century to the Present*, ed. Albert D. Van Nostrand & Charles H. Watts II (New York: The Liberal Arts Press, 1959), 345-346.

Persian – and so despised by the “chief priests and scribes” as an inferior.

I consider this Pound’s best poem written in 1909 at the age of 24, before he developed an obsession with the evils of usury. The poem has not got the recognition it deserves, being rarely included in anthologies that feature his work. Considered notorious for his approval of Mussolini and others of a like political leaning, and famous for his editing of T. S. Eliot’s ‘The Waste Land,’ Pound has spot-lighted the essence of Christ’s dealings with his hostile critics and murderous opponents, each stanza encapsulating his ability to parry their attacks, silence them, and evade their clutches. My comments on the poem are restricted to offering references to the Gospels, clarifying the various aspects of Christ that the poem depicts, stanza by stanza.

“Ballad of the Goodly Fere” by Ezra Pound

Simon Zelotes speaking after the Crucifixion. Fere = Mate, Companion.

1. Ha’ we lost the goodliest fere o’ all
For the priests and the gallows tree?
Aye lover he was of brawny men,
O’ ships and the open sea.
2. When they came wi’ a host to take Our Man
His smile was good to see,
“First let these go!” quo’ our Goodly Fere,
“Or I’ll see ye damned,” says he.
3. Aye he sent us out through the crossed high spears
And the scorn of his laugh rang free,
“Why took ye not me when I walked about
Alone in the town?” says he.
4. Oh we drank his “Hale” in the good red wine
When we last made company,
No capon priest was the Goodly Fere
But a man o’ men was he.
5. I ha’ seen him drive a hundred men
Wi’ a bundle o’ cords swung free,

- That they took the high and holy house
For their pawn and treasury.
6. They'll no' get him a' in a book I think
Though they write it cunningly;
No mouse of the scrolls was the Goodly Fere
But aye loved the open sea.
 7. If they think they ha' snared our Goodly Fere
They are fools to the last degree.
"I'll go to the feast," quo' our Goodly Fere,
"Though I go to the gallows tree."
 8. "Ye ha' seen me heal the lame and blind,
And wake the dead," says he,
"Ye shall see one thing to master all:
'Tis how a brave man dies on the tree."
 9. A son of God was the Goodly Fere
That bade us his brothers be.
I ha' seen him cow a thousand men.
I have seen him upon the tree.
 10. He cried no cry when they drave the nails
And the blood gushed hot and free,
The hounds of the crimson sky gave tongue
But never a cry cried he.
 11. I ha' seen him cow a thousand men
On the hills o' Galilee,
They whined as he walked out calm between,
Wi' his eyes like the grey o' the sea,
 12. Like the sea that brooks no voyaging
With the winds unleashed and free,
Like the sea that he cowed at Genseret
Wi' twey words spoke' suddenly.
 13. A master of men was the Goodly Fere,
A mate of the wind and sea,
If they think they ha' slain our Goodly Fere
They are fools eternally.
 14. I ha' seen him eat o' the honey-comb
Sin' they nailed him to the tree.

Commentary

- Stanza 1: ‘the priests and the gallows tree’: Mt 27:12;
 Mk 15:1, 13; Lk 23:4; Jn 18:35.
 ‘Aye lover he was of brawny men: Mt 4:18, 21.
 ‘O ships and the open sea’: Mt 8:24; Mk 4:36-39.
- Stanza 2: ‘First let these go!’: Jn 18:8.
- Stanza 3: ‘Aye he sent us out through the crossed high
 spears’: Lk 22:49-53.
- Stanza 4: ‘Oh we drunk his “Hale” in the good red wine’:
 Mk 14:22-25.
- Stanza 5: ‘I ha’ seen him drive a hundred men’: Mk. 11:15-17.
 ‘Wi’ a bundle o’cords swung free’: Jn 2:15.
- Stanza 6: ‘They’ll no’ get him a’ in a book I think’:
 Jer 51:60.
- Stanza 7: ‘I’ll go to the feast’: Jn 7:8-14.
- Stanza 8: ‘the lame and blind’: Lk 14:13, 21.
- Stanza 9: ‘I ha’ seen him cow a thousand men’: Jn 8:59.
- Stanza 10: ‘the hounds of the crimson sky’: Lk 23:44-45.
- Stanza 11: ‘They whined as he walked out calm between’:
 Lk 4:28-30.
- Stanza 12: ‘Like the sea that he cowed’: Mt 8:23-27; Mk 4:39.
- Stanza 13: ‘A mate of the wind and sea’: Jn 21:4-11.
- Stanza 14: ‘I ha’ seen him eat o’ the honey-comb’:
 Lk 24:42.

After the Lord’s resurrection, in consonance with his special link with Peter, the angel’s message to the three women who had gone “very early in the morning” to the sepulchre was, “he is risen: he is not here . . . But go your way, tell his disciples and Peter that he goeth before you into Galilee” (Mk 16:6-7), and though John outran Peter “and came first to the sepulchre . . . yet went he not in,” but “Simon Peter following him . . . went into the sepulchre, and seeth the linen clothes lie” (Jn 20:4-6), a generous recognition by John of Peter’s closeness to the Lord.

In conclusion, then, this entire scenario, I suggest, gives the reader a vivid picture of a process of moral development

and maturity in Peter who, like all of us, had both positive and negative features.

In the opening chapters of the Acts of the Apostles Peter takes the initiative in establishing the truth of Christ as “a Prince and a Saviour, for to give repentance to Israel, and forgiveness of sins” (Acts 5:31; also 2:5, 22; 3:12); and the descent of the Holy Spirit on the day of Pentecost (Acts 2:1-4).

But a greater trial awaits Peter in chapter 10 of Acts when he “went upon the housetop to pray . . . he became very hungry, and would have eaten: but while they made ready, he fell into a trance” and saw “a great sheet knit at the four corners” containing “wild beasts, and creeping things, and fowls of the air,” and a voice, “Rise, Peter; kill, and eat.” Shocked and revolted, Peter dares to disobey: “Not so, Lord; for I have never eaten any thing that is common or unclean.” But the voice rebukes him thrice, “What God hath cleansed, that call not thou common.”

Peter has now to learn the hard lesson that the Gospel is meant for all, for Jew and Gentile alike, for “God hath shewed me that I should not call any man common or unclean” (v. 28). Paying heed to the voice that he heard, Peter acknowledges the correction he needed:

And when there had been much disputing, Peter rose up, and said unto them, men and brethren, ye know how that a good while ago God made choice among us, that the Gentiles by my mouth should hear the word of the gospel, and believe. And God, which knoweth the hearts, bare them witness, giving them the Holy Ghost, even as he did unto us. And put no difference between us and them, purifying their hearts by faith But we believe that through the grace of the Lord Jesus Christ we shall be saved, even as they (Acts 15:7-11).

As is well known to readers of the new Testament, the conversion of Paul and the martyrdom of Stephen (Acts 7:57-60; 8:1-3 and 9:1-16) are events of tremendous importance that follow Peter’s “sermon” (Acts 2:14-36)

superbly captured in the words of England's Poet Laureate John Betjeman (1906-1984):

Then in a sudden blinding light
 Paul knew that Christ was God all right
 And very promptly lost his sight.
 Poor Paul! They led him by the hand
 He who had been so high and grand
 A helpless blunderer, fasting, waiting,
 Three days inside himself debating
 In physical blindness: 'As it's true
 That Christ is God and died for you . . .'¹⁰

Peter, we must note, graciously relinquishes his right to claim that to him had been revealed to "not call any man common or unclean," the apostle Paul now having that honour: "Even us, whom he hath called, not of the Jews only, but also of the Gentiles" (Rom 9:24) and in the same chapter, "What shall we say then? That the Gentiles, which followed not after righteousness, have attained to righteousness, even the righteousness which is of faith" (v. 30), and later, to Timothy, Paul writes "whereunto I am appointed a preacher, and an apostle, and a teacher of the Gentiles" (2 Tim 1:11). Yet more explicitly, Paul writes to the Galatians concerning the rift that developed between him and Peter,

When they saw that the gospel of the uncircumcision was committed unto me, as the gospel of the circumcision was unto Peter; For he that wrought effectually in Peter to the apostleship of the circumcision, the same was mighty in me toward the Gentiles; And when James, Cephas, and John, who seemed to be pillars, perceived the grace that was given unto me they gave to me and Barnabas the right hands of fellowship; that we should go unto the heathen, and they unto the circumcision . . . But when Peter was come to Antioch, I withstood him to the face, because he was to be blamed. For before that certain came from James, he did eat with the Gentiles: but when they were come, he

¹⁰ John Betjeman, 'The Conversion of St. Paul' in *Collected Poems*, ed. Andrew Motion (London: John Murray, 2006), 382-384.

withdrew and separated himself, fearing them which were of the circumcision (Gal 2:7-12).

I have gone into considerable detail concerning this rift between Paul and Peter, two of the foremost apostles, in the matter of the Gentiles having an equal status with the Jews, so as to show how consistent Paul was regarding his position as the apostle for the Gentiles, and how Peter faltered – but more importantly – how Peter adjusted himself and came to recognize the correctness of Paul's stand.

Towards the end of his life Peter anticipated with justifiable pride his forthcoming martyrdom (Jn 21:18 & 2 Pet 1:14)¹¹ and recognized the spiritual stature of Paul who, though a late comer to the rank of apostleship, declared he “was not a whit behind the very chiefest apostles” (2 Cor 11:5). Now, neither competitive nor envious, Peter writes concerning Paul, “And account that the long suffering of our Lord, is salvation; even as our beloved brother Paul also according to the wisdom given unto him hath written unto you; As also in all his epistles, speaking in them of these things...” (2 Pet 3:15-16).

Appropriately, the last words of Peter before his martyrdom are “But grow in grace, and in the knowledge of our Lord and Saviour Jesus Christ. To him be glory both now and for ever. Amen” (2 Pet 3:18), a glowing and glorious exhortation for every believer to take to heart and cherish.

¹¹ According to traditional belief, when sentenced to death by crucifixion, Peter asked to be crucified up-side-down so as not to infringe on the iconic image of Christ on the cross.